

Legacy and Luxury of Indian Cotton Textile Industry: From the lens of Indian Knowledge System

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Abstract:

India, historically known as 'Bharat,' had a rich legacy in cotton textile production, influencing global markets since ancient times (Indus-Sarasvati Civilization). The traditional Indian chintz, calico, and muslin were especially famous, which helped Bharat establish a strong presence in the global textile market. The fine quality of Indian cotton and the mastery of craftsmen in creating intricate designs were unparalleled. The **objective** of this study is to explore the unique knowledge system that underpins the Indian cotton textile industry, encompassing traditional techniques, indigenous practices, and the intergenerational transfer of knowledge. The **research methodology** employed in this secondary study is literature survey. The **findings** of this research highlight the multifaceted nature of the Indian knowledge system (IKS) in the cotton textile industry. It explores the intricate techniques of spinning, weaving, dyeing, and printing that have been passed down through generations. These techniques encompass the utilization of traditional tools, such as the spinning wheel and handloom, and the employment of natural dyes derived from plants and minerals.

Keywords: British colonialism, Chintzes and Calicos, Cotton textile industry, Indian knowledge system, Textile heritage

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1. Ancient India and legacy of cotton textile

Ancient India demonstrated an exemplary prowess in the production and export of cotton textiles, dating back to the Indus Valley Civilization (2600-1900 BCE), when cotton was first spun and woven into cloth. Archaeological excavations at *Indus-Sarasvati* Civilization, one of the significant city sites of this civilization, revealed fragments of cotton cloth and traces of cotton cultivation, signalling the advanced level of textile manufacturing during this era. Furthermore, in the ancient Maurya period (322-185 BCE), the sector was so organized that cotton textiles were used as a medium of exchange in barter. In the ancient text of Arthashastra, as translated [1] [2], it is noted that those artisans who crafted silk, wool, and cotton textiles were often bestowed with gratifying presents such as aromatic fragrances and floral garlands as tokens of encouragement. Different regions developed distinct weaving techniques and designs, such as the intricate ikat or tie-dye method from Gujarat and the highly skilled Jamdani weave from Bengal. During the classical age of the Gupta Empire (320-550 CE), Indian cotton textiles gained international acclaim. Hence, this rich legacy in cotton textile production placed ancient India at the forefront of technological, economic, and cultural exchanges.

This study aims to investigate the distinctive knowledge system supporting the Indian textile sector, which includes conventional methods, cultural practices, and the transmission of knowledge from one generation to the next. Furthermore, it seeks to understand the rich allure and distinctiveness of cotton that has been prevalent since antiquity in different parts of the world. The specific techniques and strategies intrinsic to the Indian Knowledge System that have facilitated the survival, evolution, growth and resilience of the cotton textile industry has also been analyzed. It is also inclined to assess the impact and continued relevance of the IKS in the contemporary

cotton textile industry, with a focus on production, quality control, and global competitiveness. Historic texts have documented the widespread use of Indian muslin, a luxurious fabric once used to wrap Egyptian mummies [3]. The Overseas Historical Archives in Lisbon noted in their official records of 1794 that from the 1780s, Zuarates became the most sought-after fabric. This preference was so pronounced that Vashambadzi would not accept any other type of clothing. During the time of the Rozvi Empire, royal monarchs were presented with top-quality Gujarati clothing and fabrics during their coronation ceremonies [4]. These high-quality textiles were also gifted to the Mhondoro, the spirit medium of Mutapa. The state head consistently recognized Zimbabwe with these exquisite textiles. The fabric types such as Canequims, Sofala, Samateres, Cutonias (a blend of silk and cotton with a striped pattern), Capotins, and Ardians were integral to mercantile trade. The Doutsins and Capotins were considered luxury goods, favoured by the elite class [5]. Towards the end of the 18th century, in Delagoa Bay, the demand for Gujarati textiles saw a significant increase, coinciding with economic growth.

2. Luxury status of cotton consumers in ancient times

In ancient times, cotton fabric wasn't just a common material but a symbol of luxury and wealth. Originating from the skilled artisans of the Indus Valley, cotton was admired for its lightness and quality. It wasn't just a piece of cloth but indicated a person's social and economic status. Rulers and nobles showcased their wealth and power by wearing extravagant cotton garments during public and religious events. Cotton's popularity wasn't confined to India; it was a prized item in international markets and even used as a form of currency. For instance, in the 1600s, Indian cotton textiles were bartered for spices from Indonesia as a unit of exchange. From being a symbol of affluence in ancient societies to becoming a global trading commodity, cotton's journey reflects its significant cultural, social, and economic influence throughout history.

3. Methodology

This study uses secondary data, including ancient texts and modern scholarly works, to explore the history of the Indian cotton textile industry. A literature review involved examining journal articles, books, manuscripts, and historical records to gain insights into the industry's ancient state. Archival research provided access to a hub of historical documents, including government reports and economic analyses, with records from the East India Company and British colonial administration being notably informative. These resources have been analyzed to understand the industry's context and evolution, considering the political, social, and economic conditions of each era. The study also includes a comparative analysis, contrasting the state of the textile industry during British rule and ancient times with its current state, offering a detailed view of its transformation over the centuries. The combination of these methods has enabled a thorough exploration and documentation of the Indian cotton textile industry's involved history to its soul.

4. Ancient texts mentioned about Cotton

Indian textiles, particularly cotton, have been renowned for their superior quality and craftsmanship since ancient times. This recognition is well documented in various ancient texts and historical records, painting a vivid picture of the high esteem held for Indian cotton globally. Starting with local texts, the Arthashastra, a significant treatise on statecraft authored by the ancient scholar Kautilya, sheds light on the importance of textile production, in Mauryan society. These texts also detailed different classes of weavers and the variety of textiles they produced, highlighting the diversity and complexity of India's textile industry. In the classical age of the Gupta Empire, the demand for Indian textiles, including cotton, reached far beyond its borders. The Roman historian Pliny the Elder, in his work 'Natural History', dedicated passages to the textiles from India. He called Indian cotton 'woven winds' due to their lightness and fine quality, an epitome to the excellence of Indian weavers.

Furthermore, the ancient maritime trading manual 'Periplus of the Erythraean Sea' from the 1st century CE, documents the trade of fine muslin and cotton from the ports of the Ganges delta in modern-day Bangladesh to markets across the Red Sea, Egypt, and the eastern Mediterranean. This text underscores the significant demand for Indian cotton textiles in the international markets, a clear indication of their high quality. In Arab literature too, Indian textiles received high praise. The 10th-century Arab merchant Sulaiman described Indian cotton as 'a remarkable product that resembles the fluff of the reed, more delicate than the petals of a rose'. Arab traders played a critical role in disseminating Indian textiles throughout the Middle East and North Africa.

The travelogues of Marco Polo, the 13th-century Venetian explorer, bear further testimony to the grandeur of Indian textiles. He described the Indian city of Quilon, now Kollam, as 'one of the best cities in the world for trading', where merchants traded precious spices, ivory, and 'cloths of cotton, finely woven and of different colours'. Even

Chinese Buddhist records from the Tang Dynasty mention the prestigious cotton textiles of India, which were often presented as tribute to the Chinese court. These textiles were highly cherished, and it is said that Empress Wu Ze Tian had a particular fondness for them. These accounts, spanning multiple cultures and centuries, illustrate a consistent admiration for Indian cotton and textiles. The fact that these descriptions endure in various texts, despite the passage of time and changing historical contexts, is a tribute to the skills of Indian artisans and the enduring appeal of their creations. It serves as an affirmation of the integral role Indian textiles have played in shaping global trade, cultural interactions, and historical narratives.

5. Unique Cotton Production Technology in Ancient Times: An In-Depth Exploration

The production of cotton textiles in ancient times was a multi-faceted process that combined advanced technology, skilled craftsmanship, and deep cultural traditions. It was an intricate art form, nurtured and perfected over centuries. The unique technology and techniques were used in cotton production in ancient times. The roots of cotton cultivation and production go back to the Indus Valley Civilization, where archaeological findings have suggested the cultivation of cotton as early as 2600 BCE. The ancient people of the Indus Valley not only cultivated cotton but developed tools and techniques for ginning (separating cotton fibres from their seeds), spinning (turning the fibres into thread), and weaving (turning the thread into fabric).

Ginning was likely carried out using simple handheld rollers, a technique still used in some rural parts of India. For spinning, they developed the spindle whorl, a device that increases the efficiency of the spinning process by maintaining the motion of the spindle. Clay models of such devices have been found in Harappan sites. Weaving technology varied across different regions and eras. The backstrap loom, pit loom, and frame loom were among the commonly used looms in ancient India. The complexity of the loom depended on the intricacy of the patterns and the skills of the weavers. Some regions developed specific techniques and patterns, such as tie-dyeing in Gujarat or Jamdani in Bengal, which further enhanced the appeal of the cotton textiles. Furthermore, the ancient Indians mastered the art of dyeing. Natural dyes were extracted from various plants, flowers, bark, roots, and even insects. Indigo, a blue dye, was among the most prevalent, with India being one of the largest producers in ancient times. The knowledge and skills for cotton production were often passed down through generations. This generational knowledge transfer ensured the survival and adaptation of these techniques, helping maintain the high quality and variety of cotton textiles produced in ancient India. Ancient Indian cotton production was a confluence of art and science. It was a culmination of keen observation of nature, technical ingenuity, and aesthetic sensibility. The mastery of the cotton production process led to a proliferation of trade, wealth, and cultural exchange. Moreover, the durable and eco-friendly nature of these practices have valuable lessons for our contemporary world, reminding us of the importance of sustainable and mindful production.

6. Community Cotton Connect

Local communities have always played a pivotal role in producing handloom cotton fabric sustainably and organically. They have deep-rooted knowledge of eco-friendly practices and traditional techniques, which prioritize environmental stewardship. These communities cultivate organic cotton without harmful chemicals, preserving soil health and biodiversity. Handloom weaving, a low-energy process, further contributes to sustainability. Additionally, local artisans often employ water-efficient methods, reducing wastage and promoting responsible water usage.

Table 1: Community crafting the unique Textiles/Fabrics/Designs

Textile/Fabric/Design	Name of Community	State
Khadi	Khatri	Gujarat
Jamdani	Weavers' from Nadia district and Bardhaman district	Bengal (Present day West Bengal and Bangladesh)
Bandhani & Ajrakh	Khatri	Gujarat, Rajasthan
Chanderi	Weaver's community	Madhya Pradesh
Sambalpuri Ikat	Bhulia community	Odisha
Pochampally Ikat	Padmasali community	Telangana
Kanchipuram Silk	Kaikolar community	Tamil Nadu
Phulkari	Jat Sikh community	Punjab
Dabu	Chhipa community	Rajasthan
Kalamkari	Chitragars community	Andhra Pradesh, Telangana
Patola	Salvi community	Gujarat

Ethical labour practices are prevalent, ensuring fair wages and safe working conditions. Through their collective efforts, these communities foster a sustainable and organic approach to handloom cotton production, preserving cultural heritage while supporting a greener and more socially responsible textile industry. For instances, the Bagru fabric undergoes a treatment process involving Fuller's earth (multani mitti) and turmeric (haldi). It is then hand-stamped with intricately carved wooden blocks and dyed using natural earth-toned dyes.

Table 2: Colours with the respective Natural Dyes/Source Ingredient of the Colour and the Tree, Plant/Insect for extraction

Name of the Colour	Natural Dyes / Source Ingredient of the Colour	Extracted from Which Tree, Plant, or Insect
Indigo	Indigotin (True Indigo)	Indigofera tinctoria (Indigo) plant
Madder Red	Alizarin (Madder Root)	Rubia tinctorum (Madder) plant
Reds and pinks	Camellia sinensis	Chay-root
Yellow	Curcumin (Turmeric)	Curcuma longa (Turmeric) plant
Black	Iron salts and tannins (Catechu/Black Cutch)	Acacia catechu (Catechu or Cutch) tree
Orange	Lawsone (Henna)	Lawsonia inermis (Henna) plant
Red	Carminic acid (Cochineal)	Extracted from cochineal insect
Green	Chlorophyll (Leaf Green)	Extracted from various green leaves
Brown	Catechol (Cutch)	Acacia catechu (Catechu or Cutch) tree
Violet	Anthocyanin (Plant Violet)	Berries, flowers, and leaves of various plants
Beige	Tannin (Oak Tannin)	Extracted from various trees and shrubs, particularly oak

The colour dyeing plays a crucial role in textile production in the Indian subcontinent. Traditional methods involve extracting natural dyes from organic and mineral sources such as plants and the earth, which are then applied to yarn or fabric. Dyeing techniques vary across different regions.

7. Virtuosity of Bharatiya Fabric as depicted in Kautilya's Arthashastra, Jainism, and Buddhist Literature

The history of Bharatiya fabric, particularly cotton, is steeped in antiquity and its brilliance, technique, and virtuosity find special mention in several ancient texts, including Kautilya's Arthashastra, Jain, and Buddhist scriptures. Kautilya's Arthashastra, written by the ancient scholar and advisor Kautilya (also known as Chanakya) in the 4th Century BCE, offers profound insights into the societal, economic, and political life during the Mauryan Empire. Among its diverse subjects, it encompasses details about the textile industry, highlighting its relevance in the economy and society of the time. The Arthashastra describes various types of textiles, the methods of their production, and the structure of the textile industry, revealing a highly organized and developed sector. Further, the treatise also underscores the professional status of textile workers and artisans, mentioning the rewards and incentives provided to them, thus highlighting the significant value placed on their skills and contributions.

Meanwhile, Jainism, as preached by Lord Mahavira, is another profound source of information about the contemporary textile industry. Jain texts, such as the Kalpasutras, (different types of fabrics like 'kappasi kadusam' and 'kappasikasuttam,') indicating the central role of cotton ('kappasi') in the textile industry. Jains, known for their strict adherence to non-violence, also promoted the use of plant-based fabrics like cotton, further popularizing it. Buddhist literature too is replete with references to the textile industry of the time. Terms like 'khoman', 'kosseyam', 'kappasikam', 'tantuvaya', 'tantaka', and 'tantavitatathanam', 'tantabhandam', referring to various types of fabrics and aspects of the textile industry, recur in Buddhist Jataka tales and Vinaya Pitaka. 'Tantu' (thread), is often used in the context of weavers and weaving. The use of the term 'kappasikam' once again points to the importance of cotton. The mention of 'tantuvaya' (weaver) and 'tantabhandam' (a load of threads) alludes to the socio-economic importance of the weaving profession and the widespread trade in textiles. What these texts collectively reveal is the virtuosity of Bharatiya fabric. The technical sophistication required to produce such a wide variety of textiles, the cultural importance ascribed to them, the economic value they held, and the role they played in societal, religious, and spiritual discourse - all point towards a rich, thriving, and respected tradition. Moreover, these texts suggest a society where art and craft were integral to life, and where the craftspeople were accorded a place of honor.

These ancient scriptures - Kautilya's Arthashastra, Jain, and Buddhist texts, while being spiritual, philosophical, and political guides, also serve as a historical record, providing valuable insights into the craft traditions of the

time. The admiration for Bharatiya fabric they express is an authentication to the high degree of skill, creativity, and knowledge possessed by the artisans of ancient India. Their works, crafted with immense precision and care, reflect a deep understanding of materials, techniques, and aesthetics, passed down through generations, creating an enduring legacy that continues to inspire and influence even today. Through these ancient texts, we understand that Bharatiya fabric, particularly cotton, was not just a material product but an integral part of the cultural, spiritual, and economic fabric of the society.

8. Indian Cotton clothed the world in Ancient Times

The historical narrative of Indian cotton and its profound influence on global trade provides a glimpse into a network of trade routes, and the exemplary craftsmanship of Indian artisans. Indian cotton, since its advent, has been a highly iconic item, forming the backbone of India's exports and fostering economic ties with numerous countries. Dating back to the Harappan civilization (2600 BCE), India began its journey as a pioneer in cotton cultivation and production. The knowledge and mastery of spinning and weaving cotton into fine fabrics gave birth to a robust textile industry, creating commodities that were greatly sought after both locally and internationally.

The sophisticated maritime trade networks of the ancient world facilitated the spread of Indian cotton far and wide. Archaeological and literary sources suggest that cotton textiles were among the significant commodities traded between ancient India and the civilizations of the Middle East, Egypt, and Rome. The Greco-Roman world developed a fascination for Indian cotton, with texts like the 'Periplus of the Erythraean Sea' specifically mentioning Indian cotton textiles among the imports into Roman territories. The high demand for Indian cotton in Rome was such that Pliny lamented the drain of Roman gold to India in exchange for its luxury textiles. This shows the significant role Indian cotton played in boosting India's exports and establishing its reputation as a hub of high-quality textile production. Indian cotton also made its way into Southeast Asia, significantly influencing the textile traditions of the region. Archaeological findings of Indian cotton textiles in countries like Indonesia, Philippines, and Thailand bear testimony to this exchange. Ancient Chinese records and Buddhist texts too make several mentions of Indian cotton, with the cloth often being presented as tribute to the Chinese imperial court.

The Islamic conquests of the 7th and 8th centuries further extended the reach of Indian cotton. The Arabs, who controlled the lucrative spice trade, also became conduits for Indian textiles, including cotton, to the Middle East and North Africa. Arab merchants and travellers, like Al-Masudi and Sulaiman, mentioned the quality and popularity of Indian textiles in their accounts, thus promoting the global appeal of Indian cotton. The presence of Indian cotton in Africa can be traced back to the Swahili coast's trading cities, which acted as a commercial bridge between India and Africa. Archaeological excavations have revealed fragments of Indian textiles, suggesting a vibrant Indian Ocean trade. Indian cotton textiles were not just trade items but also markers of social status among the Swahili elites.

Indian cotton's widespread appeal lay in its quality, diversity of designs, and the high level of craftsmanship involved in its production. Different regions of India developed unique weaving and dyeing techniques, contributing to the diversity of the textiles. Indian cotton, yearned for its quality and aesthetic appeal, fostered economic relationships with numerous countries, boosting India's exports, and placing it firmly in the ancient global trade network. Its impact continues to resonate, as India remains a significant player in the global cotton industry today.

9. Decline of the Indian Textile Industry: A Historical Perspective

Traditional Indian textile methods include hand spinning, where cotton fibers are pulled and twisted using spindles like the "Charkha" and "Takli," to create yarn. This yarn is then woven on different types of handlooms, like pit, frame, and "khadi" looms, to make fabrics with intricate designs. Natural dyes from plants, minerals, and insects color these fabrics. Techniques like block printing and screen printing add beautiful patterns. India's textile styles are diverse, thanks to the country's rich cultural roots. Even as machines have modernized the industry, many artisans still practice ancient crafting methods. Efforts from the government and organizations are in place to preserve these traditional skills, providing training and support to artisans.

However, the golden age of Indian textiles faced a decline due to political unrest and colonial rule. The British East India Company initially fueled the boom of Indian textiles but later contributed to its downfall with the introduction of the Calico Acts. These acts restricted the import of Indian textiles to England to protect the local industry. The British Industrial Revolution further hampered Indian textiles as cheaper, machine-made fabrics flooded the market.

Colonial rule exploited India's textile industry. Raw cotton was shipped to England, and Indian markets were forced to sell low-priced British goods. This, along with high taxes and unfair pricing, led to widespread poverty among Indian artisans and a decline in traditional crafting skills.

Despite these historical setbacks, the legacy of Indian textiles, marked by its magnificent designs and craftsmanship, has prevailed. Today, the sector is a blend of tradition and modernity, with ongoing efforts to revive and sustain the rich textile heritage that has defined India for centuries. Each piece of fabric woven and dyed by skilled hands tells a story of resilience, cultural richness, and the undiminished spirit of Indian artistry. The Indian Cotton Textile industry has faced several challenges throughout history and continues to face some today, as it seeks to grow and sustain itself. Here are some of the key challenges:

1. **Colonial Exploitation:** The industry suffered under British colonial rule when imported goods were favoured over local produce, leading to the decline of the indigenous cotton industry.
 2. **Technology Gap:** The lack of modern technology and machinery has made it challenging for the industry to compete with global counterparts. This is especially the case with handloom sectors that have not been able to keep pace with advances in textile technology.
 3. **Infrastructural constraints:** The lack of proper infrastructure, including transport facilities, adequate power supply, and other necessary amenities, has consistently posed difficulties.
 4. **Intellectual Property Issues:** Many artisans are unaware of Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), leading to the loss of exclusive rights over traditional and unique designs. This ignorance has left open opportunities for exploitation and counterfeits of designs.
 5. **Slump Productivity:** Low labour productivity and low yield of cotton farms compared to other countries make it difficult for the industry to compete on a global scale.
 6. **Cost of Raw Materials:** The cost of raw materials, especially cotton, has been rising steadily, putting pressure on the profitability of the sector.
 7. **Competition:** Indian cotton textiles face fierce competition both domestically and internationally, from synthetic materials and machine-made textiles respectively.
 8. **Lack of Marketing and Branding:** There is a lack of proper marketing and branding strategies to promote Indian cotton textiles at the global level.
 9. **Lack of Skilled Labour:** While the industry provides employment opportunities to a large number of people, there's a shortage of trained and skilled labour.
 10. **Environmental Concerns:** The cotton industry is also facing increasing pressure to become more sustainable, given the environmental impact of cotton farming and dyeing processes.
- Addressing these challenges requires concerted efforts from the government, industry, and the weaver communities to ensure the sustainable growth and preservation of the Indian Cotton Textile industry.

10. Indian Textiles, Patents, and Geographical Indications (GI) Tags: A Confluence of Tradition, Innovation, and Protection

Indian textiles, synonymous with cultural richness, historical legacy, and diverse craftsmanship, have long commanded global admiration. However, in an era defined by increasing globalization and mass production, preserving these traditional textile practices, and protecting the rights of artisans has become crucial. Herein lie the roles of patents and Geographical Indications (GI) tags, two significant legal tools that aid in safeguarding IPR and maintaining the exclusivity of Indian textiles. Patents, by definition, are exclusive rights granted to an inventor for a novel product or process, providing a temporary monopoly to the patent holder. While patents are generally associated with technological advancements, they play an essential role in the textile industry, particularly regarding innovative machinery, processes, or textile compositions. For instance, inventions enhancing the efficiency of weaving looms, improving dyeing methods, or developing new fibre blends could be patentable. Patents encourage innovation by providing inventors exclusive rights to profit from their inventions, ensuring a return on investment and further research and development.

The textile industry, following agriculture, stands as India's second-largest source of employment. Approximately 45 million people are employed directly within this sector, with an additional 60 million individuals benefiting indirectly through related activities. Do we really have a proportionally similar number of IPRs in Indian Textile sector? This needs to be considered crucially. However, most traditional Indian textile practices are the result of collective community knowledge passed down through generations, making them unsuitable for patent protection, which usually protects individual or corporate inventions. This is where GI tags come into play. A Geographical Indication (GI) is a sign used on products that have a specific geographical origin and possess qualities or a

reputation attributable to that origin. GI tags help protect traditional products closely tied to their place of origin. For Indian textiles, GI tags have been instrumental in safeguarding the interests of artisan communities, maintaining the unique identity of different textile styles, and boosting their economic value. By linking a product to its place of origin, GI tags help authenticate and preserve the quality, technique, and heritage associated with it. A classic example is the GI tag granted to Pashmina products from Kashmir. Known for its fine quality and exquisite craftsmanship, authentic Pashmina is made of cashmere wool obtained from a particular breed of goat native to the high altitudes of the Himalayas. The GI tag helps protect this craft from imitations and assures consumers of the product's authenticity. Similarly, the hand-woven Banarasi Sarees, known for their intricate designs and rich use of gold and silver zari, received a GI tag in 2009. The tag not only protects the unique weaving technique and reputation of Banarasi sarees but also supports the livelihood of thousands of weavers in the region. Another example is the Madhubani/Mithila paintings of Bihar, a traditional art form often replicated on textiles, which was granted a GI tag in 2018, protecting the authentic art and its practitioners.

The patents and GI tags are two significant mechanisms that uphold the heritage and stimulate innovation in the Indian textile industry. While patents protect novel inventions and encourage technological advancements, GI tags play a crucial role in preserving traditional textile crafts linked to specific regions. Together, they help maintain the uniqueness of Indian textiles, support the livelihoods of artisans, and contribute towards a more sustainable and equitable textile industry. The challenge remains to effectively implement these protective measures and ensure that the benefits reach the artisans, the true bearers of India's rich textile heritage.

11. Continuity of Ancient Indian Textiles and Production Methods: Tradition in the Modern World

India boasts a rich textile heritage, rooted in traditional practices like hand spinning and handloom weaving. Despite the dominance of machine-made textiles, India's artisanal craftsmanship endures, celebrating age-old techniques. From the delicate muslins of Bengal to the vibrant silks of Kanchipuram and Banaras, each piece encapsulates the meticulous labor and skill of the artisans. Block printing, a technique with origins in the ancient Indus Valley Civilization, and natural dyeing methods are still employed. It is resonating with the global shift towards sustainable fashion. Yet, the competition from mass-produced, cost-effective machine-made textiles threatens these traditional crafts, prompting initiatives to safeguard and revive these timeless arts. Traditional practices such as block printing and natural dyeing contribute to the country's vast textile variety. Techniques like Dabu and Bagru printing, using hand-carved blocks and natural dyes, appreciating India's artistic flavor. Despite the challenges posed by machine production and low compensation for artisans, efforts to uphold these arts are significant. Various initiatives offer platforms for artisans, financial and technical assistance, and aim to educate the public on these crafts' cultural and economic worth.

India's textile legacy is not just a celebration of the past but a mean of sustainable and ethical fashion's future. Governmental and non-governmental bodies have inculcated measures to support and protect these crafts. Initiatives like the Handloom Mark scheme ensure quality and promote Indian handloom globally. The Cluster Development Program and the Geographical Indication Act empower artisans, preserving the unique heritage of traditional textiles and offering defense against unauthorized use. Despite these crafts' labor-intensive nature and the lure of machine-made alternatives, a global and domestic demand surge for handcrafted, sustainable products pushes life into traditional practices. The government, NGOs, and social enterprises are at the forefront, weaving together modern designs with traditional methods, ensuring their relevance on contemporary fashion arena. Each weave and stitch, imbued with the essence of generations of craftsmanship, epitomizes not just aesthetic grandeur but a profound narrative of cultural richness and sustainable ethos.

In today's context, cotton's omnipresence as a staple fabric aligns with its comfort and durability. However, distinct elements and craftsmanship can elevate it to luxury status. The indigenous processes and skills involved in traditional textile creation are a testament to the artistry and heritage that imbues each piece with unique value. Efforts to uphold these traditions amidst a world dominated by fast fashion underscore the dynamic interplay between preserving historical craftsmanship and navigating modern consumer demands. Each piece of traditionally crafted textile thus embodies a narrative of resilience and cultural richness, offering more than just material value – a piece of history, art, and the enduring spirit of Indian craftsmanship. The following factors contribute to cotton's luxurious appeal for consumers:

1. Superior Quality and Artistry: Luxury cotton often signifies excellent quality and craftsmanship. Renowned brands and designers may prefer high-quality cotton varieties like Egyptian or Supima cotton, known for their plush, strong, and lavish feel. These elite types of cotton, painstakingly grown and boasting longer, finer fibers,

result in superior and long-lasting fabrics. Moreover, the artisan skills involved in weaving, finishing, and detailing cotton garments can boost their luxurious appeal.

2. **Unique Design and Branding:** Luxury cotton garments usually showcase unique, intricate designs, one-of-a-kind patterns, and keen attention to detail. Prestigious fashion brands and designers use their skills and creativity to produce distinctive cotton wear that exudes exclusivity. Brand reputation and image significantly contribute to enhancing the prestige of cotton consumers. Brand-conscious consumers often correlate luxury with certain labels and pursue their cotton products for their perceived quality, reputation, and style.

3. **Exclusive Editions and Personalization:** The luxury quotient of cotton apparel can be amplified by offering limited edition or exclusive collections. These limited production batches, or partnerships with famous designers or artists, render these items rare and coveted. Customization adds an element of luxury, with tailor-made or bespoke cotton clothing, allowing consumers to select specific fabrics, accents, and details for a unique and exclusive experience.

4. **Sustainable and Ethical Measures:** Nowadays, the focus on sustainability and ethical practices has significantly influenced the luxury status of cotton consumers. Consumers increasingly opt for brands that endorse eco-friendly cotton cultivation, fair trade, and supply chain transparency. Cotton products derived from organic or sustainably-sourced cotton, manufactured with minimal environmental impact, are seen as luxurious due to their ethical and responsible production processes.

5. **Pricing and Scarcity:** The cost of cotton garments can also add to their luxury status. Although cotton is generally cheaper than other luxury fabrics like silk or cashmere, specific high-end cotton products can carry a higher price tag. Factors like limited supply, exclusivity, and brand positioning can affect the perceived value and desirability of cotton items, marking them as a luxury buy for consumers.

It's worth mentioning that luxury perceptions can vary between individuals, and different cultural contexts may shape what is deemed luxurious. Various factors such as quality, craftsmanship, design, branding, exclusivity or customization, sustainability, and pricing can influence the luxury status of cotton consumers in contemporary times. In essence, the journey of ancient Indian textiles and their production methods is one of remarkable endurance and adaptability. As we navigate through the 21st century, it is crucial that we continue to honour and uphold this rich textile legacy, supporting the skilled artisans and sustainable practices at its heart. After all, these traditional crafts are more than just fabric and thread - they are the narratives of India's cultural heritage, artistic prowess, and timeless innovation.

12. Recent Government Initiatives to Safeguard the Ancient Textile Industry in India

India's textile tradition, an amalgamation of a rich cultural heritage and skilled craftsmanship, has been a vital part of the country's socio-economic fabric for centuries. Recognizing this, the Indian government has initiated a few recent measures to preserve, promote and provide support to this vibrant sector. These initiatives, often aimed at boosting the productivity and global appeal of Indian textiles, provide financial, technical, and marketing aid to artisans. One such initiative is the National Handloom Development Programme (NHDP). Launched by the Ministry of Textiles, it seeks to develop and promote the Indian handloom sector by providing financial assistance for new looms and accessories, capacity building, and the creation of new design inputs. The program also facilitates better access to raw materials and markets, empowering weavers and improving the competitiveness of the handloom sector. The Handloom Mark Scheme, another significant initiative, has been introduced to assure consumers about the genuineness of hand-woven products. By providing a distinct identity to handloom products, it promotes the branding of Indian handloom products both within the country and for export. The government, recognizing the importance of geographical indications (GI) in protecting and promoting unique Indian textiles, has been proactive in registering several traditional textile forms under the Geographical Indications of Goods (Registration and Protection) Act 1999. These include Pochampally Ikat, Banarasi Sarees, Chanderi Fabric, and Muga Silk of Assam, among others. This not only safeguards these textile traditions from unauthorized use but also enhances their market appeal by authenticating their geographical origin.

Under the umbrella of Make in India initiative, the government has also taken steps to attract foreign investments in the textile sector, aimed at technological upgradation and skill enhancement. This initiative aims to make India a global hub for textile manufacturing and design, thereby creating more opportunities for traditional textile artisans. The Ministry of Textiles also launched the Samarth Scheme for capacity building in the textile sector. This scheme focuses on skill development, providing training to many individuals in various segments of the textile sector, including traditional textiles and handicrafts. The Cluster Development Program is another key initiative, aiming to uplift artisan communities by providing them with essential infrastructure, new technologies, and training

in improved techniques. By grouping artisans into clusters, the program facilitates easier distribution of resources and a better exchange of skills and knowledge. Moreover, the government has been increasingly leveraging digital platforms to bring Indian textiles closer to global consumers. The India Handloom Brand is an initiative to endorse the quality of handloom products in terms of raw material, processing, and product compliance to specifications. Through an online portal, it provides a platform for weavers to showcase their products to a broader audience. These initiatives reflect the Indian government's dedicated efforts to uphold the country's rich textile legacy. By integrating tradition with technology and local skill with global market access, these programs aim to ensure a vibrant and sustainable future for the Indian textile industry.

13. Findings

Thomas Ellison and Robert Robson, in "The Cotton Trade of Great Britain" and "The Cotton Industry in Britain," outlined the colonial oppression that transfigured India's prestigious textile industry. The East India Company's strategic moves downgraded a nation, once a significant exporter of cotton textiles, into a subjugated importer, pushing local farmers into a cycle of poverty and debt, and disrupting an economy once vibrant with indigenous craftsmanship. The British enforced rigid pricing and adopted manipulative technologies, establishing an era of unfair competition, biased taxation, and prejudiced duties. The Indian textile sector, a mosaic of diverse traditional fabrics and artistic expressions, faces the challenge of ignorance towards Intellectual Property Rights (IPRs) among local artisans. The potential for economic and cultural elevation lies latent, awaiting the recognition and patenting of unique designs crafted by tribal and regional artisans. However, the grandeur of handmade textiles is overshadowed by the industrial prowess of global machine-made fabric producers. This scenario underscores the dire need for a revival, where IKS is not just preserved but revered. The artistry of spinning, weaving, and dyeing, enriched by generations of cultural transmission, is evident to India's heritage. By illuminating these practices, we advocate for a paradigm where tradition is not just a reflection of historical grandeur but a living entity - evolving yet rooted in the timeless legacies of craftsmanship.

14. Relevance to Contemporary Times

The conventional mode of designing and weaving Indian cotton fabric holds significant relevance in contemporary times for a variety of reasons. Firstly, with the implementation of the National Education Policy (NEP), integrating the IKS in the cotton textile industry's curriculum from an early age can instil a sense of cultural pride and appreciation for traditional practices among students. This knowledge transfer will help preserve and promote India's rich heritage. Secondly, empowering the youth with skillsets in this traditional craft enhances their self-employability and fosters the spirit of "Aatmanirbhar Bharat". By nurturing a generation of skilled artisans, the country can reduce unemployment and boost its socio-economic growth. Thirdly, the global image of India can be significantly enhanced by conserving and promoting its cultural heritage through handloom cotton fabric. As sustainable and eco-friendly products gain recognition worldwide, India's reputation as a responsible and traditional textile producer will flourish. Moreover, the conventional mode of designing and dyeing fabrics offers sustainable solutions, contributing to the zero-waste industry. By utilizing natural dyes and eco-friendly techniques, this approach aligns with contemporary demands for environmentally conscious practices, attracting environmentally conscious consumers. Lastly, the current trend of de-dollarization presents an opportunity for India's exclusive textile exports. By focusing on creating premium products that demand payment in Indian Rupees, the nation can reduce its dependence on foreign currency and strengthen its economic independence. In conclusion, embracing the conventional mode of designing and weaving Indian cotton fabric aligns with contemporary needs and aspirations. It not only nurtures cultural identity but also contributes to skill development, sustainability, and economic autonomy. By preserving and promoting this traditional art form, India can carve a unique niche in the global textile market while staying true to its rich heritage.

15. Conclusion and Policy recommendations

Embracing traditional Indian cotton fabric design and weaving promotes cultural preservation, sustainable practices, and economic growth. Integrating vocational training and sustainability measures, like organic dyes and energy efficiency, equips the youth with skills and minimizes environmental impact, while protecting intellectual property rights. Enhancing global market access through e-commerce and ensuring fair trade and compensation for artisans fosters equity and economic empowerment. To put it simply:

1. Government and educational institutions should collaborate to introduce certification programs and vocational training focused on handloom weaving and dyeing techniques.

2. Encouraging research and investments in sustainable practices, such as organic dyes and energy-efficient production methods, will help in achieving a greener and eco-friendly textile industry.
3. Stringent measures must be put in place to protect the IPRs of traditional designs and techniques, safeguarding the artisans' heritage.
4. Government agencies and non-profit organizations should create awareness campaigns to inform artisans about available financial support and grants to support their craft.
5. Promote market development by collaborating with industry experts to create e-commerce platforms that connect artisans directly with global consumers.
6. Establish fair trade policies to ensure artisans receive fair compensation and social security benefits, guaranteeing their well-being and improving their livelihoods.

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